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Design Methodologies in The Software Development Process

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Abstract

Methodologies are an important aspect of the development process and can greatly impact the outcome and quality of the resulting product. This paper explores the methodologies involved in the development of the software process, and what methodologies are, as well as, various use cases for methodologies within software development. This paper describes a few different design methodologies and their differences, as well the application of Design Thinking in the development process. This paper also discusses the implications of switching methodologies, and why it might be worth the trouble to switch.

Software development is, as defined by IBM, on their website, www.ibm.com, in their article, “What Is Software Development?” as “a set of computer science activities dedicated to the process of creating, designing, deploying and supporting software.” (What is software development?) Software development teams are brought to make new or existing projects (Sawyer). This process is used to develop systems from high level applications, such as applications like complex social media applications, or a simple calculator app. Or low-level software applications, like operating systems such as, Microsoft Windows, Linux, or Mac OS. According to Steve Sawyer in the paper, “Software development: Processes and performance.”, Sawyer states, “A methodology represents the set of tasks, and their ordering, that sets out the processes of production.”. These tasks make up the methodology and allow for a concise and simplified way to develop software. There are other factors to software development besides the methodology, such as techniques, and the tools used to construct the software (Sawyer). Sawyer goes on to say, “Techniques are sets of actions taken to complete a particular task.”

Methodologies are made up of these many sets of actions that we call techniques (Sawyer).

For many years, developers used what is referred to as “traditional methodologies” (Matharu). Traditional software methodologies are very process focused, very high in documentation, and less focused on users (Matharu). These methodologies are typically more focused on sustainability instead of adaptability and have heavy comprehensive planning ahead of development (Matharu).

Some of the Methodologies for the software development process include, Design thinking, Agile, Lean Startup (Dobrigkeit). Design thinking has five elements: Emphasize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, Test (Brenner). “Emphasize”, or sometimes called “Observe” is understanding the perspective of the user of the product, the customer. During this phase designers gather everything they need, through things like lab and field experiments, or surveys. This process allows for a more human centered approach, and negates problems of over engineering, as designers are able refine exactly the user experience should be (Brenner). “Define” is the next step in the design thinking process, this is the part where designers target the specific needs of the user, after the Emphasize phase, define is where designers sort out all the research previously done on users, and incorporate it into the development plan (Dam). Once the “defining” part of the process has been completed, it is time to move on to the next step in the process, “Ideate.” During this process, designers are trying to brainstorm, and look at the problem from different angles (Dam). After “Ideate”, the next step in the process is Prototyping, this is the part of the process when designers turn something conceptual into a tangible product for testing (Brenner). Using this small scaled tangible product, the designers are able to identify solutions to various problems that were discovered during the previous stages (Dam). The next, and final step during the design thinking process is testing. This allows to accelerate the learning process (Brenner). Testing the product and going through all these steps allows the developers to gain a better understanding of the product, and how the product will interact with the users (Dam). Using this method, design thinking can help with innovation by using these processes. By taking the steps outlined previously, Emphasize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, Test, it gives a process that developers can easily follow to help foster innovation. It helps break down the big project of, “we must fix this problem”, into little steps that make solving the problem more

manageable. Instead of trying to attack the development of software aimlessly, using the design thinking's, Emphasize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, process allows for each section to be broken up into these small parts. It allows for complex projects to become broken up into small pieces throughout the process, and it allows for problems in the project to be found within the various stages. Another role of Design thinking is the big emphasis on empathy and understanding the client. In Jon Kolko's article, "The divisiveness of design thinking", Jon Kolko states, "It promotes "empathy lite"—as if an empathetic and meaningful connection with people could be forged in hours or even days.", While Jon Kolko has a point that it takes more than a few hours to form a meaningful connection, at least design thinking places emphasis on the importance of connections with the client and users, while other models neglect to even consider connections with people. Such as, the waterfall methodology which fails to even consider the client all together and makes a point to not involve them (Adenowo).

A more common methodology for software is the agile method, The Agile method is the most popular methodology used in software development (Jensen). According to Matilde Bisballe Jensen, in the "Empirical Study of Agile Software Development Methodologies", Jensen states, "In Agile approach to software development, work is carried out in small phases, based on collaboration, adaptive planning, early delivery, continuous improvement, regular customer feedback, frequent redesign resulting into development of software increments being delivered in successive iterations in response to the everchanging customer requirements." (Jensen). This approach also has a focus on the end user, and though agile is quite similar to design thinking, there are a few differences. While design thinking and Agile both make the end user involved, agile fails to carefully consider and focus on the actual design part of the product (Dobrigkeit). Design thinking is not without flaws, and no methodology is, design thinking fails

when it comes to scalability (Dobrigkeit). Once the design thinking process is over, it is done. There is no going back through and redoing the project, that would mean scratching everything, and then starting the process over. Of course, designers could implement *parts* of the design thinking process, such as the prototype or the testing, but that is not really the design thinking methodology, design thinking is the entire process of, “Emphasize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, Test”. This is what makes design thinking powerful; it has an order to be followed.

Another popular design methodology for software is the “waterfall method”, this method breaks up the process in distinct steps, with each step having a specific goal in mind for that step (Adenowo). The steps of the waterfall methodology process are, Requirement Analysis, Design, Implementation, Testing, Operation, and Maintenance (Adenowo). Once the phase is completed, the next step proceeds, however, there are “Modified Waterfall” methods which make this more flexible. It allows for phases to cross into other phases to make developing the product more flexible for the engineers (Adenowo). The traditional waterfall methodology uses a sequential development model, and everything is finished before moving onto the next phase, and the requirements are clear before each phase starts (Adenowo). One of the downsides of this model is that, while it is thorough, it is time-consuming, and as a result takes more time to complete. One of the reasons the waterfall method is so time consuming is because each phase requires approval before moving onto the next one, since with the waterfall method, once you move into the next phase, you cannot move backwards. Meanwhile, speed is a key component of both agile and design thinking, with speed even being the namesake of agile, and design thinking cutting down on steps, allowing for it to be completed faster (Agile vs design thinking: Key differences and similarities). Design thinking, Agile, and other methodologies all have their own pros and cons. Agile is great for products that have a predefined problem, and designers need to solve

something that is already recognized as a problem (Agile vs design thinking: Key differences and similarities). While design thinking can help with finding the problems that need to be solve, without knowing the problem initially, so this can help speed the overall process up in the long run, as problems can be found out along the way, and not just as they pop up in production (Agile vs design thinking: Key differences and similarities).

Waterfall is a lot different compared to the Agile methodology, the Waterfall is not just rigid, it is a core aspect of the methodology, the agile methodology pushes the focus of the methodology into the users and allows for significant adaptability (McCormick). According to Mike McCormick, in “Waterfall vs. Agile Methodology “, Mike McCormick says, “Compared to the 'set-in-stone' approach of waterfall development models, the agile breed of models, focus on 'agility' and 'adaptability' in development.” (McCormick). The two methodologies take two completely different approaches to achieve the same goal.

While design thinking has not been as popular with software development, it has been growing in popularity in other disciplines, such as business (Liedtka). In, “Design Thinking: What it is and Why it Works”, by Jeanne Liedtka, Liedtka states, “University of Potsdam have begun a multi-phase project to examine how design thinking is being incorporated into the development process within the IT industry.” As well, as discussing a study involving about approximately a hundred Thai businesses, on the relationship between performance and design thinking (Liedtka). The study found no correlation between innovativeness and the performances of the firms. However, the study within the IT industry found that the processes are key to producing more innovative outcomes (Liedtka). So, this indicates while it may not be as useful in business, where it is starting to become more popular, it could be more viable in the tech industry where it is lacking. More positive research where studies show promising results may increase

the desire and need for design thinking in the tech industry, which might cause more and more firms to abandon the other prominent methodologies that they rely on. Software company, AppHaus, has implemented Design Thinking methods for product discovery but the agile method for their implementation and testing (Jensen). In an article written by SumatoSoft, an IT Development Company, in their article titled, “What Design Thinking Is and How It Is Used in Software Development”, SumatoSoft goes into talking how to incorporate design thinking into software development (SumatoSoft). The article discusses how design thinking can help with some design issues, SumatoSoft uses the example of buttons, and how a “Yes”, and “No” being colored as, red, and green, could be confusing. So even the little details of designing UI can be important and design thinking can help mitigate this issue (SumatoSoft). These problems can be found in the “define” stage and then hopefully solutions can be found in the ideate step (SumatoSoft). According SumatoSoft’s article, SumatoSoft mentions, “With the help of design thinking approach, developers pass all stages, from empathy to testing, and strive to provide users with a solution that would make the search across products as fast and convenient as possible. They carefully consider all elements, arrange them logically and do everything to make customer journey as comfortable as possible.” (SumatoSoft). This would allow developers to conveniently find problems and create solutions that they find in their product throughout the stages, while keeping in mind the client/user. If developers start to incorporate design thinking into their development pipeline, then this can be beneficial to both the developers and users or clients. When client problems can be found at the beginning/throughout the process of development, it can allow the problems to be mended for the final product. This saves time and money, because the client’s problems can be found at the very beginning, instead of weeks into launch of a final product when it might be more costly and time consuming to fix the problems at

arise after launch. Design thinking also allows for transparency, as SumatoSoft also mentions, by saying, “Design thinking approach allows software developers to see and clearly understand the end goals, problems and have a detailed vision of the solution they should eventually deliver” (SumatoSoft). This is a great thing, developers being able to understand the end goals and have a vision of a solution can save time, and money, which ultimately will benefit both developers and clients. The clients will receive software that adequately fits their needs and concerns, and developers will save time and money. It also allows for continuous improvement within the software in certain circumstances, which again also saves time and money (SumatoSoft). SumatoSoft says, “The product can be (and sometimes should be) modified after its release when user feedback is at hand”. Which would ensure that user’s concerns are being fixed throughout the lifetime of the product. Which means that the product can continue to be viable for the product to make a profit, if continuous development continues that means that users that would otherwise leave the product forever, can have their concerns met and fixed. This would allow for long-term users, which in theory, would mean sustainable profit for certain applications (SumatoSoft). According to Rikke Dam and Teo Siang, from the Interaction Design Foundation, in their paper, “What is Design Thinking and Why Is It So Popular?”, they go on to explain how design thinking is not just for designers, but for everyone. Saying, “Design Thinking is not an exclusive property of designers—all great innovators in literature, art, music, science, engineering, and business have practiced it.” (Interaction Design Foundation). Everyone benefits from the design thinking model, including software developers. Rikke Dam and Teo Siang go on to say, “Design thinking begins with skills designers have learned over many decades in their quest to match human needs with available technical resources within the practical constraints of business”, design thinking, just naturally, is multidisciplinary, and allows for disciplines for grow

from the mutual benefit of each other.” (Interaction Design Foundation). Software developers could greatly benefit from incorporating design thinking, as well as other disciplines. In Jennifer Hehn’s paper, "The Use of Design Thinking for Requirements Engineering: An Ongoing Case Study in the Field of Innovative Software-Intensive Systems.", Hehn’s states in the paper, “Our findings hint at a “morphing nature” of [Design Thinking] in software-intensive development projects, evolving from process-guidance”. Design thinking is changing, and this could possibly be due to the general flexibility of design thinking (Hehn). The flexibility of design thinking can also be beneficial to the development process (Hehn). Modification of the methodology to help fit the intensive process can help the team slowly phase into the design thinking method. Software developers can slowly start to incorporate the small elements of design thinking into their development pipeline, developers and firms do not need to just instantly switch to design thinking, as that could be abrasive to the workflow, instead the developers can take small pieces and slowly start to piece it together from their usual workflow, if they are using agile methodology, they can take pieces of design thinking and see if they work before making the full switch. If more developers make the switch to design thinking or at least attempt to incorporate some of the elements of the design thinking, they may find that works better for a multitude of different projects. While the agile methodology might be more equipped to handle certain types of software compared to other types of software development, the flexibility of design thinking allows for it to be applicable to a large variety of design thinking. In Farley Fernandes, paper “Gamethinking: a Roadmap to a Design Thinking-based Model for Game Development Education”, Farley Fernandes states, “Gamethinking, aims at using DT as more than a creativity process, but also as a changer of the culture, mindset, and behavior of game development students, addressing issues such as cognitive models, belief systems, and learning behavior

through gamification and ludology fundamentals.” Farley Fernandes’s research discusses the implementation of design thinking into the game development process, in the form of merging design thinking with agile methodology (Fernandes). Now, changing methodologies can be a challenging task for a business to achieve, even if it would be overall beneficial for the company. Sridhar Nerur mentions in, “Challenges of Migrating to Agile Methodologies.”, that, “Past research shows that software development process changes represent complex organizational change phenomena and cannot be accomplished merely by replacing current tools and technologies with new ones”, these kinds of changes need to be made slowly, and accordingly to ensure that process can be properly accomplished (Nerur). Nerur goes on further in the piece to say, “Agile methodologies are ideal for projects that exhibit high variability in tasks (because of changing requirements), in the capabilities of people, and in the technology being used” and that embracing agile methodologies can look very attractive for companies due to the perks of agile, but that organizations should be prepared in switching, as it can be a massive undertaking. (Nerur). There are a lot of factors that play into the switching of a methodology for development, such as the existing technology. Companies relying on outdated equipment may have difficulty switching methodologies (Nerur). While it can be difficult and challenging at first to switch methodologies, over time the long-term benefit of switching can help. Instead of using old techniques that rely on more process/design focused approaches, instead of newer user focused approaches (Nerur). Switching the methodology can also help with overall scalability of projects, which could also be a great benefit and appealing reason to switch (Nerur). So, while switching methodologies might be messy, depending on how integrated the previous methodologies are it can be a worthwhile investment depending on the needs of the developers. Developers should weigh their options in deciding what methodology might be for them. If developers need a low

budget, user focused methodology, then the agile method might be well suited for them (Matharu).

Overall, the design methodology that is used by the developer can have a great impact on the resulting product. The Design thinking methodology encompasses a streamlined way of not only problem solving but problem finding. The Waterfall methodology is more rigid and allows for the work to be more carefully considered before moving on. The agile methodology is meant to be fast and efficient and reliant on the users. Developers should use a methodology that works best for the project at hand, that could be the rigidness of the waterfall methodology, or the speed of agile methodology, or even the flexibility of design thinking methodology. The choice of methodology should depend on the project specs, and there should be an understanding of the methodologies and how it might be best applied to the project. Using Design Thinking can be integrated into the process slowly, instead of abruptly, if a firm is always using a different design methodology. It is important to consider all factors when choosing a methodology, and the implications of switching methodologies.

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